

DESIGN OF LOW POWER AND AREA EFFICIENT APPROXIMATE MULTIPLIER WITH REDUCED COMPLEXITY USING ENCODED PARTIAL PRODUCTS AND VEDIC MULTIPLICATION

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ABSTRACT: The heart of any electronic gadget is the arithmetic and logic unit. Having an effective algorithmic operation, such multiplication and addition, is crucial for an arithmetic and logic unit to be essential in the current improvement. Machine learning, artificial intelligence, neural networks, and digital signal processing all rely on multiplication. The size, power, and latency of electronic devices determine their performance in the very large scale integration (VLSI) domain. The importance of approximation computing for error-tolerant applications has skyrocketed. As a result, there is a significant improvement in computing performance within an acceptable error range, and there is additional optimisation in terms of space and power. Therefore, both the performance and the error characteristic are taken into account equally. An area-and power-optimized design for an error-tolerant multiplier is introduced in this paper. Using approximation at the lower level of partial product allows for a trade-off with the error characteristic. Various multipliers' results are shown, including area, power, and error factor. By using the suggested method, a significant improvement is accomplished.

1. INTRODUCTION

As technology advances, more and more IT applications are realising the need for low-power integrated circuits (ICs) to handle massive amounts of data. The size also rises

as a result of interconnected applications. Multiplying the power usage by the computing time yields the energy efficiency. In order to come up with a solution that is energy efficient, the designer has to cut down on both power usage and computation time. One way to lower the static power is to cut down on logic blocks. There is a trade-off connection between power consumption reduction and circuit performance, although many strategies have been successful in this regard [1]. Decreased power for many electronic systems and subsystems, consumption has become the primary design objective. First and foremost, according to the creators, are the inbuilt-powered sensor modules [2]. An integral aspect of any computer system's hardware architecture, processing units also happen to be the most power-hungry component [9]. In order to fulfil computer efficiency requirements while adhering to stringent power constraints, new design strategies are required [10]. A number of applications, including Machine Learning (ML), Computer Vision (CV), Image and Video Signal Processing, and others, benefit from approximate or inexact computing as a superior and more promising technique [11]. Less time spent computing results in substantial energy savings [1]. Quite a lot situations when mistakes are purposefully made, and where it is more practical to employ an approximation calculation due to the difficulty in detecting little mistakes. These kinds of situations often arise when

we're trying to compress or decompress images by separating the intensities. Approximate computing is the most effective and efficient way to create low power circuitry for the aforementioned applications. The truth remains, nevertheless, that speed and area are incompatible performance requirements. Thus, expanding the area is a natural consequence of improving the pace of innovation. When applied to an FPGA, the suggested design improves the speed performance of the well-known Wallace tree multiplier. The traditional Wallace multiplier undergoes structural optimisation to significantly lower the entire circuit delay. If the partial products in the $n-k$ least significant columns are all ones or all zeros, then the maximum error for a truncated multiplier with constant correction is zero. Someone suggested a truncated multiplier with configurable correction. Based on column $n-k-1$, this technique modifies the corrective term. The corrective term is raised if every partial product in column $n-k-1$ is a one. The same holds true for this column; a drop in the corrective term occurs when all partial products are zero. An easier way to construct bigger multiplier arrays is using a 22-multiplier block. Compressors have been extensively used in the construction of fast multipliers to lower power consumption and speed up the partial product reduction tree. Compression for approximation multiplication has also been investigated by Ma et al. and Kelly et al. It has been suggested to use an approximate signed multiplier in mathematical data value speculation (AVDS); the Baugh Wooley method is used to do multiplication. But given the imprecise calculation, no new compressor design is suggested.

LITERATURE SURVEY

High-performance and energy-efficient approximate multiplier for error-tolerant applications by S. Kim and Y. Kim, Approximate computing in the arithmetic logic has recently emerged as a promising solution for energy-efficient designs in

error-tolerant applications. So not only the performance but also the error characteristic become important criteria. In this study, we propose a high-performance and energy-efficient approximate multiplier with suitable error characteristics by using low energy approximate adders for lower bits. Simulation results of 16×16 multipliers show that area, delay, and power saving are significantly improved by the proposed multiplier compared to the conventional binary multiplier.

In addition, error metrics of the proposed multiplier have shown better results than other approximate multipliers.

Approximate Multipliers Based on Inexact Adders for Energy Efficient Data Processing by M. Osta, A. Ibrahim, H. Chible and M. Valle

Approximate computing circuits are considered as a promising solution to reduce the power consumption in embedded data processing. This paper proposes an FPGA implementation for an approximate multiplier based on inexact adder circuits. The performance of the proposed multiplier is evaluated by comparing the power consumption, the accuracy of computation, and the time delay with those of an approximate multiplier based on exact adder presented in literature. Results reports a

power saving up to 17.39% with an improvement in time delay by 13.49%, at cost of less than 5% of accuracy loss. Power and Delay Efficient Exact Adder for Approximate Multiplier by V. V. Kavipranesh, J. Janarthanan, T.

N. Amruth, T. M. Harisuriya and E. Prabhu, Approximate results are required in many embedded data processors as they reduce time delay and power. As error tolerance adder (ETA) has decreased power drastically trading with accuracy. This work

focuses on reducing delay on existing adders when replaced with a fast adder. When compared to the past works on ETA, the proposed work has high power utilization and more accuracy of speed. The proposed design is compared and synthesized for the power and delay. When observed the existing ETA designs, the proposed work achieves significant improvement in power dissipation about 17.13%, 4.6%, 15.4%, 5.35% decrement for 4, 8, 16, 32 bits respectively, and significant improvement in delay about 28.90%, 23.59%, 20.08%, 24.44% decrement for 4, 8, 16, 32 bits respectively.

3 EXISTING SYSTEM

The algorithm of WALLACE multiplier is based on the below matrix form. The partial product matrix is formed in the first stage by AND stages

Fig.1 4x4 WALLACE Algorithm
Steps involved in WALLACE TREE multipliers Algorithm

Multiply (that is - AND) each bit of one of the arguments, by each bit of the other, yielding N results. Depending on position of the multiplied bits, the wires carry different weights.

Reduce the number of partial products to two layers of full adders. Group the wires in two numbers, and add them with a conventional adder.. Product terms generated by a collection of AND gates.

Fig2 Product terms generated by a collection of AND gates.

Wallace Tree Multiplier Using Ripple Carry Adder

When there are a lot of adds to be done with linked carry ins and carry outs, the ripple carry adder is the way to go. Therefore, a ripple carry adder employs a number of adders. Multiple complete adders may be connected in a logical circuit to add integers with more than one bit. With each complete adder, we get the preceding adder's Cout as an input, or Cin. A ripple carry adder is the name given to this kind of adder because each carry bit "ripples" to the next complete adder thereafter. Figures 9–11 show the suggested design of the WALLACE multiplier algorithm that makes use of RCA. Put any three values into a complete adder with the same weights. The end product will be a wire with the same weight as the input. The first step is to take the partial product that results from multiplying. Each stage's carry is added to the following two data's in after the data is taken with three wires and added using adders.

the same stage. Partial products reduced to two layers of full adders with same procedure. At the final stage, same method of ripple carry adder method is performed and thus product terms p1 to p8 is obtained.

Fig 3 .4x4 Wallace Multiplier Implementation.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Wallace Tree Multiplier (WTM) is yet to be considered as a hardware efficient arithmetic circuit [20]. After a generation of partial products using N2 AND-Gates (for N-bit multiplier), compressors are used to add. An accurate 2-bit multiplier will generate maximum “1001” when A [1:0] = “11” and B [1:0] = “11”. Other input combinations will generate the result less than or equal to “110” which can be represented by 3 binary bits.

Eliminating the MSB of the 4-bit result of an accurate multiplier, the multiplier will result “001” instead of “1001” with an error magnitude of 8 for A[1:0] = “11” and B[1:0] = “11” combination. The functional table is given in TABLE I to represent the reduced functionalities by masking the carry bit in 2-bit multiplier. Using the 2-bit multiplier, the higher bit multipliers can be designed with an increased Error Factor (EF).By using K-Maps, the Boolean Functions are expressed as shown in Eq. 1 to Eq. 3. The circuit implementation can be realized as shown in Fig. 1.

$$P[0]=A[0].B[0] \tag{1}$$

$$P[1]=A[1].A[0].B[1]+A[0].B[1].\overline{B[0]}+A[1].\overline{A[0]}.B[0]+A[1].\overline{B[1]}.B[0] \tag{2}$$

$$P[2]=A[1].B[1].B[0]+A[1].A[0].B[1] \tag{3}$$

A trade-off is made in terms of accuracy to optimize the power and area. The Boolean equations are given for a 2-bit multiplier, where A[1:0] and B[1:0] are the input vectors and P[2:0] is the output vector. The multiplier is truncated for a trade-off in accuracy and logic gates. The manipulated functionality is given in the TABLE 1 and its logic in Fig.

1.Now replacing the output by “111” in TABLE I for input A[1:0] = “11” and B[1:0] = “11”, the error factor can be reduced to 2. Secondly, the Boolean expressions are simplified further and shown in Eq. 4 to Eq. 6.

$$P[0] = A[0] . B[0] \tag{4}$$

$$P[1] = A[0] . B[1] + A[1] . B[0] \tag{5}$$

$$P[2]=A[1] . B[1] \tag{6}$$

TABLE I. FUNCTIONALITY OF 2-BIT APPROXIMATE MULTIPLIER

Inputs		Outputs
A [1:0]	B [1:0]	P [2:0]
00	00	000
00	01	000
00	10	000
00	11	000
01	00	000
01	01	001
01	10	010
01	11	011
10	00	000
10	01	010
10	10	100
10	11	110
11	00	000
11	01	011
11	10	110
11	11	001

Using 4-variable K-Map the simplified Boolean expressions are derived and given in Eq. 4 to Eq. 6.

Fig.4. Simplified Reduced Partial Product Architecture

In first stage, partial products $A[0]B[0]$, $A[0]B[1]$, $A[1]B[0]$ and $A[1]B[1]$ are generated. The partial product results in a 3-bit output and adder stages are eliminated as shown in Fig. 2. Six 3-input AND-Gates are replaced by 3 two-input AND Gates. This gives an area efficient solution with improved accuracy.

Fig 5. Reduced Partial Product Multiplier with Less EF and Area

The operation of 4-bit multiplier can be explained using Fig. 3 as shown in two stages. In first stage operands are grouped and multiplication is carried out using 2-bit multipliers. The outputs of the first stage are added up to derive the result. Using similar techniques, 8-bit multiplier is designed. The Architecture of a 4-bit error-tolerant multiplier is shown in Fig. 4 and an 8-bit

multiplier in Fig-5.

The operation can be explained by dividing the 4-bit operands into a group of 2-bit. The partial products are represented by solid circles. Lower part adders are used to generate the results represented solid squares.

Fig. 6. Operation of 4-bit Approximate Multiplier

The proposed architecture is shown in Fig. 3. The partial products are generated using 2-bit multipliers and the basic adders are used to derive the output. Because of reduced partial product the adder size is reduced during 4-bit and 8-bit multiplier design. The Reduced Partial Product Multiplier (RPPM) gives low-power and area efficient solution for approximate computing and error tolerant applications. The functional blocks are shown in Fig. 5 after RTL implementation.

Fig.7. 4-Bit Approximate Multiplier using RPPM

The 8x8 bit Vedic multiplier module as

shown in the block diagram in Fig. 6 can be easily implemented by using four 4x4 bit Vedic multiplier modules as discussed in the previous section. Let's analyze 8x8 multiplications, say $A = A_7 A_6 A_5 A_4 A_3 A_2 A_1 A_0$ and $B = B_7 B_6 B_5 B_4 B_3 B_2 B_1 B_0$. The output line for the multiplication result will be of 16 bits as – $S_{15} S_{14} S_{13} S_{12} S_{11} S_{10} S_9 S_8 S_7 S_6 S_5 S_4 S_3 S_2 S_1 S_0$. Let's divide A and B into two parts, say the 8 bit multiplicand A can be decomposed into pair of 4 bits AH-AL. Similarly multiplicand B can be decomposed into BH-BL. The 16 bit product can be written as:

Using the fundamental of Vedic multiplication, taking four bits at a time and using 4 bit multiplier block as discussed we can perform the multiplication. The outputs of 4x4 bit multipliers are added accordingly to obtain the final product. Here total three 8 bit Ripple-Carry Adders are required as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig 8. Block Diagram of 8x8 bit Vedic Multiplier

Multiplier is an integral part of the processor. Vedic multiplier is based on the Vedic mathematics. Vedic multiplier's architecture is based

on the Sutra called "Urdhva Tiryakbhyam". Urdhva Tiryakbhyam (Vertically and Crosswise), deals with the multiplication of numbers. This Sutra has been traditionally used for the multiplication of two numbers in the decimal number system. By applying the algorithm to the binary number system, architecture for multiplier is designed. Other sutra used for Vedic multiplier is Nikhilam Sutra which literally means "all from 9 and last from 10". Although it is applicable to all cases of multiplication, it is more efficient when the numbers involved are large. Compared with the other multipliers, Vedic multiplier has less delay time. Vedic multiplier is also used for computing Fast Fourier transform.

5. EXTENSION

Implementation of FIR Filter using proposed multiplier

A filter is a device or process that removes some unwanted component or feature from a signal. Filtering is a class of signal processing, the defining feature of filter being the complete or partial suppression of some aspect of the signal. There are two main kinds of filter, analog and digital. Filters can be classified in several different groups, depending on what criteria are used for classification. The two major types of digital filters are finite impulse response digital filters (FIR filters) and infinite impulse response digital filters (IIR).

Fig 9. Finite Impulse Response Filter Realization

One of the most common filter types used in DSP is the Fourier transform (FIR) filter. The lack of input makes FIR filters limited in their capabilities. Thus, the output will always become zero the moment an impulse (one spike) passes through the filter if we apply them to the system. There is no feedback in a non-recursive filter. Figure 10 depicts the realisation of the finite impulse response filter.

Many digital signal processing applications rely on finite impulse response (FIR) digital filters. These include software-defined radio (SDR), speech processing, loud speaker equalisation, adaptive noise cancellation, echo cancellation, and a host of communication applications. Stringent frequency requirements need large-order FIR filters for many of these applications. In order to provide ultra-fast digital communication, these filters often must be able to sustain a high sampling rate. But, as the order of the filters rises, the amount of math operations needed for each output grows linearly. It is difficult to build a large-order FIR filter in real-time in a resource-constrained setting

SYSTEM	AREA	POWER(mw)	DELAY(ns)
Existing(Wallace tree multiplier)	143	0.299	32.681
Proposed method	121	0.162	22.008

because the FIR filter method does not make use of redundant computing. It is well-known that there are apiarian signal processing applications where filter coefficients stay constant. The field of digital signal processing makes extensive use of finite impulse response (FIR) filters. Equation 1 defines an N-tap FIR filter in terms of its input and output.

The coefficients of the filter are represented as $\{h(i): i = 0 \dots N-1\}$. The convolution procedure that a FIR filter employs is frequently based on the premise that signals might have an indefinite length

[1]. In contrast, there are boundary discontinuities in finite length signals (such as pictures). Which values to apply in these areas is therefore a new issue. Extending each row by reflecting at the signal edges is an often suggested method. $N-1$ is the amount of additional samples added at the signal boundaries. The signals on the left and right sides might be divided unequally. In this context, α and μ will denote the number of samples inserted at the left side input signal ($N - 1$) and the right side input signal ($\alpha + \mu$), respectively.

6. SIMULATION RESULTS

8.1 Results

Fig 10 Simulation Result of Multiplier Here we can give the inputs as $A=3$, $B=5$, then the final output is 15.

Table 2 Comparison between existing and proposed in Area, power and delay

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Two 8-bit multipliers—one that is accurate and one that is approximate—are created using Xilinx software. With this work, we provide the "Urdhva Tiryakbhyam Sutra," an effective method of multiplication with its origins in Vedic mathematics. Hierarchical multipliers might be constructed using it, and it reveals the computational advantages of Vedic methods. Hence, our objective of reducing delay has been met. Therefore, the Vedic multiplier considerably enhances execution speed compared to the Array and Booth multipliers. Vedic mathematics has the potential to be better understood if it is included into engineering courses. Ideally, in the future, all the major universities may set up appropriate research institutes to fund studies of Vedic mathematics. Power savings of up to 33.35 percent are possible in dynamic mode, and up to 29.29 percent in static mode as compared to WTM. Using chips as an example, the suggested approximation architecture is clearly better. The reduced product method has the potential to save silicon area by 25.7%. These multipliers have a big impact on our everyday lives. Going forward, the multipliers are going to play a significant role. Accelerating the multipliers is possible using carry look ahead adders, carry save adders, and similar techniques. Which rounding patterns work best will depend on the required accuracy and the different compression techniques. Both the area and the delay may be reduced with the use of future-proof technologies.

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